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SECURE OUTSOURCED CALCULATIONS WITH HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid development of cloud computing, the privacy security incidents occur frequently, especially data security issues. Cloud users would like to upload their sensitive information to cloud service providers in encrypted form rather than the raw data, and to prevent the misuse of data. The main challenge is to securely process or analyze these encrypted data without disclosing any useful information, and to achieve the rights management efficiently. In this paper, we propose the encrypted data processing protocols for cloud computing by utilizing additively homomorphic encryption and proxy cryptography. For the traditional homomorphic encryption schemes with many limitations, which are not suitable for cloud computing applications. We simulate a cloud computing scenario with flexible access control and extend the original homomorphic cryptosystem to suit our scenario by supporting various arithmetical calculations. We also prove the correctness and security of our protocols, and analyze the advantages and performance by comparing with some latest works.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Privacy, Homomorphic Encryption, Proxy Cryptography

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